

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NYARWATI****FIRST NAME: JACOB****PROGRAM CODE : MDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Applied citations**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

My 7 key concepts with page number in text (ACA-401/401D COURSEPACK RP1) are as follows:

1. Observed issues (or mistakes) in grammar (EUCLID 2019, 29)
2. Contextual spelling (EUCLID 2019, 32-33)
3. Punctuation (EUCLID 2019, 29)
4. Sentence structure (EUCLID 2019, 18-22)
5. Style of Writing (EUCLID 2019, 44)
6. Vocabulary enhancement (EUCLID 2019, 32)
7. Quotations (EUCLID 2019, 6-13)

HOW TO WRITE A GOOD ESSAY?

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing a good academic essay requires that I follow laid down basic steps when starting, do research on the topic, organize my ideas well when writing it, and ensure that I reference all information obtained from other sources and edit the essay after proof reading before submitting (EUCLID 2019, 1-4). Therefore, if I use another author's information without referencing, this will be counted as plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5). The harm is that, "Plagiarism is wrong and unethical, it is not fair for me to take someone's work and not give them credit, it is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences" (ibid.) on me as a writer.

There are two methods of citation; in text citation which can be in form of quotations or paraphrases, and list of works cited on the bibliography /references at the end of an essay/response paper or book (EUCLID 2019, 5-13). The chapters from 11 to 26 of the Turabian manual for writers are also guiding me in the fundamental academic approach of grammar, quotes, citations and bibliography. Am advised to apply RP Normal style for body paragraphs at all levels. When writing I should use the Zotero tab in Word to add/edit parenthetical citations to be trusted. it is important to that I should choose and be consistent

with a technique although I should be aware that the style of what we write will never be perfect (Turabian 2013, 78-79).

2) PURPOSE OF THE COURSEPACK

To enhance my knowledge of figuring out errors and mistakes in a paper, essay or thesis and dissertation writing and correct them (EUCLID 2019, II). It also provides me with insight on how to write a good essay/paper or thesis. Above all it enlightens me on how I can avoid plagiarism through guided citation depending on whether am writing a response paper or a major paper (EUCLID 2019, 5-13). Finally, it stipulates clearly that when writing a paper, I must choose the style of writing (e.g., Turabian Chicago style for theses/ papers/ dissertations) and type of standard English version I will use that must remain consistent.

a) FIRST PART: THE SUMMARY

The (ACA-401/ACA-401D) course pack has nine chapters of 59 pages. Chapter one guides me on good essay writing, chapter two on citation styles, chapter three on rules guiding writing of papers, chapter four on literature review, chapter five on styles of writing and why that is important to me, chapter six on differences between standard American and standard British English, chapter seven takes me through corrections done on some sample papers, chapter eight enlightens me on CMS crib sheet and finally chapter nine defines full meaning of Latin abbreviations and expressions as used in academic paper writing.

b) SECOND PART: REACTION TO THE COURSE PACK

While I know that essay writing requires both creative and critical thinking. I have gained new knowledge on brainstorming or mind mapping as part of the process of creative thinking. Also, I have learned that critical thinking is supposed to encourage me to narrow the focus or scope of my ideas (EUCLID 2019, 2).

In most cases plagiarism is defined as “Taking someone else’s words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author” (EUCLID 2019, 5). From this ACA-401/401D RP1 course pack I have learned that, also having someone write a paper for me and then putting my name on it and giving it to my professor would be counted as plagiarism (ibid.).

i) *Plagiarism*

Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). To avoid plagiarism, I must ensure that when using any quote, paraphrase, statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source I must cite. I now know that plagiarism can corrupt

my academic paper writing integrity since its wrong and unethical, it is not fair for me to take someone's work and not give them credit and that it is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences in my course work (EUCLID 2019, 5).

ii) *Citation Styles*

Citation is used in academic paper writing as a solution to avoid plagiarism where the author or source of information used is provided (EUCLID 2019, 6). Two methods of citation have been provided in the course pack that are the most used form in academic writing: They are in-text citations, and list of works cited (ibid.).

I have briefly summarized the two methods as follows:

- 1) the in-text method, involves the use of:
 - *Quotations* Are the exact words of an author. When I use a quotation, I must use quotation marks “.” to capture what the author has said (EUCLID 2019, 6).
 - *Paraphrasing* Is defined as a state where ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic are written in my own words (EUCLID 2019, 8).
- 2) While the list of works method uses:
 - *References* of sources used at the end of the document, which provides full bibliographic information i.e. Authors Name, Date, Book Title, and Place of Publication: Publisher (EUCLID 2019, 10-11).
 - *Footnote referencing/text citations*, is where the details of information source/author are indicated within the text by the author's last name and the publication year of the work cited. No punctuation is used between the name and the date, and for direct quotations the page number is also included (ibid.)

As a writer I am required to guide readers through the text, and be consistent with one of the quote and citation style, this will help the readers to make connections, access source documents and verify, if necessary, the validity of my arguments giving evidence on which they are based; but most importantly, good referencing is essential to avoid any possible accusation of plagiarism (Turabian 2013, 208).

3) **THIRD PART: THE CONCLUSION**

Throughout this course pack (ACA-401/401D RP1) I have observed that all academic paper writing whether essay, theses or dissertation should observe the following; grammar, pronunciation, contextual spelling, punctuation, sentence structure, style, or vocabulary enhancement citation, and precise referencing in order to acknowledging the sources used in writing an essay. While different citation methods can be used in different settings, two are the most used in academic technique, both outlined in the ACA-401/401D

course pack: in- text citation and list of work citation (EUCLID 2019, 6). Finally, am advised that I should use standard methods in a consistent manner that allows the reader to access and verify the source documents, and if necessary add weight to claimed comments and arguments; moreover, a well referenced essay will avoid any possible accusation of plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13).

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: EUCLID University.

Turabian, Kate L. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.